

mlr3 Package in R to Classify and Interpret Data

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Abstract— The diagnosis of neurological diseases such as Parkinson's disease (PD) is commonly based on medical observations and assessment of clinical signs, including the characterization of a variety of motor symptoms. However, this type of diagnosis often depends on the person being evaluated, making the analyzes subjective. To deal with these problems and refine the procedures for the diagnosis and evaluation of neurological diseases, machine learning methods have been implemented for classifying and differentiating the levels of the disease. The R mlr3 package and its extension packages implement a powerful, object-oriented and extensible framework for machine learning (ML) in R. It provides a unified interface to many available learning algorithms, augmenting them with general-purpose, model-independent functionality, e.g., training test evaluation, resampling, preprocessing, hyperparameter tuning, nested resampling, and results visualization. In this article, an example of the use of this package will be presented, which may later help in the classification of motor signs in Parkinson's Disease.

Keywords — Parkinson disease, machine learning, mlr3, classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a part of computer science that aims to develop systems that simulate the human ability to perceive a problem, identifying its components to solve problems and propose/make decisions [1]. AI involves several steps or competences, such as recognizing patterns and images, understanding written and spoken language, following decision algorithms proposed by experts, being able to understand concepts, acquiring “reasonings” through the ability to integrate new experiences and, thus, self-improvement, solving problems or performing tasks [2]

Machine learning (ML) is a particular approach to the design of intelligent systems in which the system adapts its behavior based on data [3]. Currently, human involvement with systems that use AI and ML is increasing. For example, assistance-based systems like Siri, Alexa, Cortana or Google Assistant. These systems can have a great impact on people's lives, and can be used in medicine as well.

For the application and use of ML, there are several packages and toolboxes for the R language [4]. The mlr3 package for R provides a generic, object-oriented and extensible framework for classification, regression, survival analysis and other machine learning tasks [5]. This interface

is unified and provides functionality to extend and combine existing learners, intelligently select and adjust the most suitable technique for a task, and perform large-scale comparisons that enable meta-learning.

Most packages in the mlr3 ecosystem focus on processing and transforming data, applying machine learning algorithms and computing results. The mlr3 package itself provides the core functionality that the rest of the ecosystem depends on and some building blocks for machine learning [6]. Other 3rd party packages extend mlr3 with features for pre-processing, pipeline, visualization, and additional learners.

Within the field of medicine, neurology was the area that most benefited from the innovations promoted by AI, with the main applications including: robot-assisted surgery, automated preoperative planning, classification of diagnostic brain images and prediction of post-operative outcomes. - patient operations [7]. As well as the progressive increase in the use of high technologies for diagnosis and treatment in health, the increase in the prevalence of neurodegenerative pathologies, together with the rapid aging of the population, represents challenges for health systems and society in general.

In this sense, there is a wide range of technological and computational tools that can help scientific research for large-scale analysis. In this way, neurodegenerative disorders can be investigated further in order to provide a more comprehensive overview of the disease [8]. As its name implies, machine learning allows a computer program to learn and extract meaningful representations of data. By using ML approaches, we can identify relevant features that are not traditionally used in the clinical diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease (PD) and rely on these alternative measures to detect PD in pre-clinical stages or atypical forms [9].

Currently, PD diagnoses and assessments are performed using clinical scales, such as the UPDRS [10]. However, other diagnostic aids are needed to improve the accuracy of this method. Additionally, incorporating new technologies can lead to more personalized care. For example, classification using ML may provide a new method for identifying the best combination of clinically relevant spatiotemporal features for diagnosing and treating people with PD[11]. In addition, the classification may provide new methods of evaluating the progression of the disease, differentiating the levels of impairment in a more objective way.

The purpose of this article is to introduce the mlr3 tool and apply a generic example using it to sort different groups of data. In addition, provide an understanding of its application to the classification of Parkinson's disease motor signs.

II. METHODS

A. Mlr3 Structure

The main structure and the essential building blocks of mlr3 package is summarized in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Mlr3 structure summarized

The data, which mlr3 encapsulates in tasks, is divided into non-overlapping test and training sets. Using the separate test data strategy allows us to objectively evaluate models for their generalizability. The training data is fed to a machine learning algorithm, which we call a learner in mlr3. From the training data, a model is built, which is then used to produce predictions on the test data, which are compared with the truth values. In this way it is possible to assess the quality of the model.

Separating the data into training and testing sets, building a model, and evaluating it can be repeated several times, resampling different training and testing sets from the original data each time. Multiple iterations of resampling allow us to obtain a better and less biased generalizable performance estimate for a specific type of model. As data is often randomly partitioned into training and test sets, a single split can, for example, produce very different training and test sets, thus creating the misleading impression that the model performed poorly.

B. Tasks and Learners

Tasks are objects that contain the data, usually organized in tables, and metadata that define a machine learning problem. The metadata is, for example, the target variable name for supervised machine learning problems or the dataset type. Using the mlr3 tool it is possible to create different types of tasks as classification, regression, survival, density, cluster and spatial tasks. Each task is used for a different type of data, but the most common are classification and regression tasks. In the Classification task the target is a label with only relatively few distinct values. And in the Regression task, the target is a numeric quantity (stored as integer or numeric).

Objects of the Learner class provide a unified interface to many popular machine learning algorithms in R. They consist of methods for training and predicting a model for a task. All Learners work in a two-step procedure:

- Training stage: Training data (resources and target) is passed to the function that trains and stores a model.

- Prediction stage: data, usually a different slice of the original data used for training, is passed to the method. The model trained in the first step is used to predict the target.

Training a learner means fitting a model to a given set of data. We then predict the outcome for observations that the model did not see during training.

C. Resampling

It is imperative to validate the stability of your machine learning model. It is impossible to fit the model to the training data and expect it to work accurately for real data that has never been seen before. It is necessary some kind of assurance that your model has picked up most of the patterns in the data, and isn't picking up too much noise, or in other words, bias and variance should be low.

When evaluating the performance of a model, we are interested in its overall performance, that is, its performance on new data that was not previously seen in training. It is possible to estimate this performance by evaluating a model in a test set, which was created to contain only observations that are not contained in the training set. There are many different strategies to separate a dataset into training and testing, in the mlr3 package these strategies are called resampling.

Some types of strategies used in mlr3 are: cross validation, leave-one-out cross validation, bootstrapping, subsampling and custom resampling.

D. Application

With a Task, a Learner and a Resampling, we can incorporate the basic strategies for a machine learning task. In this sense, in order to understand how the mlr3 package works, an example will be presented using the generic "penguins" database [12]. The *palmerpenguin* data provided size measurements of three penguin species observed on three islands in the Palmer Archipelago in Antarctica. It is a dataset that includes several measurements from three different species of penguins, namely Adelie, Gentoo and Chinstrap.

The creation of a task and a classification learner will be presented. Then, resampling will be done 10 times and the average accuracy of the model will be presented. Applying the method to a generic database gives us an initial idea of how the package works. With this, we can later apply the same method to interpret and classify biological data and signals.

III. RESULTS

First, for a machine learning task it is necessary to create the task, we will use the *penguins* dataset for this.

```

library(mlr3) # library of mlr3 toolbox
# create learning task
task_penguins = as_task_classif(species ~ ., data
= palmerpenguins::penguins)
task_penguins # visualizing the task
  
```

With this, we can see the main parameters of the chosen dataset. The result of this first iteration is:

```

## <TaskClassif:palmerpenguins::penguins> (344 x
8)
## * Target: species
## * Properties: multiclass
## * Features (7):
## - int (3): body_mass_g, flipper_length_mm,
year
  
```

```
## - dbl (2): bill_depth_mm, bill_length_mm
## - fct (2): island, sex
```

After the task is created, we have to define which learner we will use:

```
# load classification learner
learner = lrn("classif.rpart", cp = .01)
```

With a task and a learner, we can finally train and test our model, for this we chose an 80% proportion for train set:

```
# train/test split
split = partition(task_penguins, ratio = 0.8)
# train the model
learner$train(task_penguins, split$train_set)
# predict data
prediction = learner$predict(task_penguins,
split$test_set)
# calculate performance
prediction$confusion
measure = msr("classif.acc")
prediction$score(measure)
```

The results of this prediction and the confusion matrix was:

```
##           truth
## response  Adelie Chinstrap Gentoo
## Adelie    140         5         0
## Chinstrap  6         63         1
## Gentoo    0         0        118
```

```
## classif.acc 0.963964
```

For just one iteration we obtained an accuracy of 96.3964%. However, we cannot rely solely on this result. Therefore, we must resample the training and test sets. In this sense, 10 times resampling was performed:

```
# 10-fold cross validation
resampling = rsmpl("cv", folds = 10L)
# run experiments
rr = resample(task_penguins, learner, resampling)
# access results
rr$score(measure)[, .(task_id, learner_id,
iteration, classif.acc)]
rr$aggregate(measure)
```

The result of the 10 iterations and the aggregate result were:

```
## task_id  iteration  classif.acc
## 1:         1         0.9705882
## 2:         2         0.8529412
## 3:         3         0.9705882
## 4:         4         0.9696970
## 5:         5         0.9393939
## 6:         6         0.9090909
## 7:         7         0.9393939
## 8:         8         0.9696970
## 9:         9         0.9696970
## 10:        10         0.9393939
```

```
## classif.acc 0.9430481
```

With this we can observe that for each different set of data we have different values for the accuracy of the model. Furthermore, the average accuracy for the 10 models was 94.3048%. In addition, it is possible to visualize the boxplot with the accuracy of the models tested:

```
library("mlr3viz")
autoplot(rr, measure = msr("classif.acc"))
```

Figure 2 shows the generated boxplot.

Fig. 2. Boxplot with resampling results.

IV. DISCUSSION

This article presented the use of a new tool for machine learning using the R language. Mlr3 is an easy-to-apply tool, and the great advantage is that it is based on the R language, which is free and has easy access. With the increasing number of searches for machine learning tools, it becomes even more advantageous to choose a complete package as the one presented.

In addition, this article demonstrated the importance of resampling. As we could see in the results, the difference between doing just 1 iteration or repeating 10 times using different test and training groups was relevant. Using resampling algorithms combined with ML models involves more information about the data and therefore results in less biased results [13]. In addition, the mlr3 tool presents artifices for visualizing the data, such as the boxplot. They help to better visualize the results, and make it easier to compare different models.

The example presented can be used in future studies with biological data from people with neurological disorders, such as Parkinson's Disease. In recent years, there has been an increase in studies that use machine learning to detect and differentiate the signs and symptoms of Parkinson's Disease [14]. Several methods have been studied and applied for this purpose, such as neural networks (NNs), hidden markov models (HMMs) and support vector machines (SVMs) [8], [14]. In this sense, a tool like mlr3 that is easy to apply becomes an interesting alternative against more complex methods.

As a starting point, a good classification and selection technique should be able to demonstrate those characteristics that have high correlation with the response variable (PD or healthy control classes) and minimal redundancy between the features evaluated. Therefore, there is a need to identify suitable ML modes and the optimal combination of characteristics for PD signals classification.

This work has some limitations such as a lack of comparison with other similar tools. For future studies, it is necessary to do a more detailed evaluation of the results found, as a statistical analyses and a validation of the methods using different tools with the same purpose.

V. CONCLUSION

As shown, tools like mlr3 can facilitate the application of machine learning to diverse data sets. In view of these

applications, Artificial Intelligence and machine learning can do an excellent job in terms of improving the performance of the entire process (diagnosis, prognosis and treatment) and providing more efficiency in the results.

In future studies, it is desired to apply this tool in the analysis and interpretation of physiological data from people with Parkinson's Disease, in order to understand and classify their signs and symptoms.

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